

MANUFACTURE OF HYBRID BICOMPONENT FIBERS BY KISS-ROLL COATING

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid bicomponent fibers represent a promising class of intermediate materials that facilitate the high-volume production of thermoplastic composites. Compared to existing intermediate materials, bicomponent fibers allow for very short cycle times through the minimization of flow lengths during consolidation, while retaining the high formability of dry fibrous preforms. As a method to manufacture such hybrid bicomponent fibers, we propose a kiss-roll coating process in-line with glass melt spinning. A high-speed study is presented to prove the feasibility of the process to yield fiber volume fractions appropriate for use in advanced structural composites. The influence of the fiber speed, the polymer concentration in the coating solution, and the radius and peripheral speed of the kiss-roll on the resulting coating thickness are assessed via a two-level full factorial parameter study. Finally, some considerations for the realization of a high-speed coating stage in-line with glass melt spinning are given.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic matrix materials generally enable faster manufacturing of composite parts compared to thermosetting resins, due to their absence of long curing times. Instead, thermoplastics can be melted, formed and re-solidified in a thermal cycle, which is a rather fast process, especially for thin laminates. State-of-the-art thermo-forming processes use pre-consolidated, pre-impregnated or otherwise hybridized materials – e.g. organosheets, thermoplastic prepregs, hybrid weaves or commingled yarns – as feedstock materials. Of the existing thermoforming processes, stamp forming achieves the shortest cycle times. In stamp forming, the pre-consolidated feedstock is heated above the forming temperature and then inserted into a press with an isothermal mold that is held below the solidification temperature. Upon closing of the press, the part is simultaneously cooled and formed. Stamp forming of pre-consolidated intermediate materials means that cycle times are limited mainly by the heat transfer from the matrix to the mold during solidification. The drawback of this method is that the use of preconsolidated feedstock generally limits the geometrical complexity of the component to be formed, because it provides a higher resistance to in-plane shear deformation and other draping mechanisms compared to dry preforms. An ideal preform for stamp forming would thus consist of a material which can be consolidated quickly while still being flexible enough to provide good drapability to form complex shapes.

Previously, we have proposed the use of hybrid bicomponent fibers [1, 2], a material architecture in which reinforcing fibers are surrounded by a thermoplastic sheath. These thermoplastic sheaths become the matrix material of the fiber-reinforced component when the bicomponent fibers are consolidated under heat and pressure. A preform material produced from such fibers has two main advantages: firstly, unconsolidated textile-based preforms are expected to exhibit better draping behavior and lower resistance to re-forming than pre-consolidated sheets, because the fibers can move more freely during the forming process; secondly, the architecture of hybrid bicomponent fibers provides a full wet-out, thus avoiding the need for any time-consuming impregnation flows and allowing these materials to be stamp formed directly without an additional preconsolidation step.

The manufacture of such preforms is however not trivial, since large amounts of individual filaments

need to be coated with a thermoplastic polymer. Our idea is to take advantage of the individually separated filaments in the glass fiber spinning process and implement a coating stage in-line between the bushing and the gathering shoe. Yet, this coating stage needs to be compatible with the glass spinning process in terms of fiber speed and needs to yield coating thicknesses which result in an optimal range of fiber volume content in the consolidated composite part. Previous investigations [2] on dip-coating [3] have shown that the implementation into a glass fiber spinning plant may be achieved up to speeds lower than the velocities applied in industrial fiber-glass production. Here, we study the feasibility of kiss-roll coating as a potentially faster manufacturing process for hybrid bicomponent fibers.

Kiss-roll coating is already the state-of-the-art process for sizing glass fiber rovings [4]. In this process, depicted in Fig. 1, the fluid is first transferred onto a partially immersed rotating roll, before it is picked up by the moving substrate, in this case a fiber, which only touches the roll over a short contact length, thus coining the term “kiss-roll”. Compared to dip-coating, where the substrate is withdrawn from a quasi-infinite bath, this setup introduces a flow mechanism which limits the amount of fluid available to coat the fiber. The extent of this limitation can be tuned via the thickness of the fluid layer on the kiss-roll at the point of first contact with the substrate, which is in turn controlled through the roll speed ω and dependent on the roll radius R , the angle of contact θ at which the roll mantle leaves the bath and the fluid’s density ρ , viscosity η and surface tension γ .

Figure 1: Schematic of kiss-roll coating of fibers and its process parameters.

For the same coating thickness, kiss-roll coating enables higher fiber speeds v compared to dip-coating. Note that slip between the fiber substrate and the roll is allowed and is an essential requirement for the realization of thin coatings at high substrate speeds. In such cases, the slip ratio between the substrate and the roll is positive, as shown in Eq. 1, where U denotes the peripheral speed of the kiss-roll’s mantle surface.

$$\frac{v}{U} = \frac{v}{\omega R} > 1 \quad (1)$$

We believe that kiss-roll coating with a dilute polymer solution in-line with the glass fiber spinning process is a promising method for fabricating hybrid bicomponent fibers. The higher fiber speeds compared to dip-coating allow the spinning of thinner and thus stronger glass fibers while at the same time increasing the material throughput, moving closer to the range of typical production speeds in industry. An added benefit is that kiss-roll coating is already well known for the application of sizes to the fibers.

2 OBJECTIVE

In this study, we examine the influence of the most important processing parameters on the resulting coating thickness and its sensitivity to fiber speed. The objective is to distinguish parameters which need

to be controlled accurately to achieve a robust process from those which have a lower influence, while at the same time identifying how parameters which cannot be varied during the process should best be chosen. We study a glass fiber and low melt viscosity polymer system and examine the influence of fiber speed v , polymer concentration in the coating solution w_p , peripheral roll speed U and roll radius R on the resulting coating thickness h and thus the final fiber volume fraction v_f .

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Single E-glass filaments of finite lengths (< 3 m) with a mean diameter of $12\ \mu\text{m}$ were separated from a roving containing 204 filaments sized with 1 wt% 3-aminopropyltriethoxy silane (APTES). Individual filaments were successively drawn downwards vertically by a rotary winder, touching a kiss-roll at a height of 850 mm above the winder (Fig. 2). The coatings dried at room temperature before touching the winder axis. The fiber speed v was varied for each experiment to yield coating thicknesses which correspond to fiber volume fractions v_f of the resulting hybrid bicomponent fibers between 50% and 70%.

Figure 2: Experimental setup used to coat single glass filaments.

The kiss-roll was partially immersed in a dilute solution of poly(ester-amide) (PEA) (Dow Europe) [5, 6] in trichloromethane (ReagentPlus[®] 132950, Sigma-Aldrich) at a constant angle of contact θ of 150° . The kiss-roll and bath were covered almost entirely by a hood to trap trichloromethane fumes and keep the solution concentration stable for the duration of the experiments.

High speed trials were run with a solution of 5 wt% poly(ester-amide) in trichloromethane with a

kiss-roll radius R of 0.1 m, a peripheral roll speed U of 1.88 m s^{-1} and fiber speeds v up to 14 m s^{-1} to assess the potential of the method for implementation in a glass spinning process. The finite fibers were attached to the winder axis before a step input was given to the motor drive, which meant that the rotary inertia of the setup limited its response. It was found that a fiber speed of 14 m s^{-1} was the maximum possible step input for which the winder reached the set speed before the majority of the fiber ran past the kiss-roll.

For the parameter study, the polymer concentration w_p , peripheral roll speed U and roll radius R were varied per a two-level full factorial design of experiment, as illustrated in Fig. 3 and with the values listed in Table 1. Higher polymer concentrations were chosen based on the expectation that they would promote a lower range of fiber speeds yielding appropriate coating thicknesses. The incoming and outgoing angles of the fibers, α and β (Fig. 1), were kept constant, meaning that the contact length between fiber and kiss roll scaled linearly with the roll radius R .

Figure 3: Illustration of the parameter space with sample points for the two-level full factorial study.

Parameter	Unit	Low level	High level
w_p	[wt%]	8	10
U	[m s^{-1}]	0.5	1.0
R	[m]	0.05	0.10

Table 1: Parameter space for the two-level full factorial study.

The experiments were run in random order and for each parameter set, multiple fibers were coated at different fiber speeds. The coated fibers were imaged both transverse to their axes and in cross-sections in a Zeiss LEO 1530 (Gemini column) scanning electron microscope (SEM). The cross-sections were realized by mounting the specimens in epoxy and by subsequent grinding and polishing. They were used to determine the mean diameters \overline{D}_c of the glass cores. The transverse images were measured for the distribution of outer diameters $D_{p,i}$ of the polymer coatings. The obtained values were squared and divided by the square of the mean core diameter to yield the specimen's fiber volume fraction distribution $v_{f,i}$ (Eq. 2).

$$v_{f,i} = \frac{\overline{D}_c^2}{D_{p,i}^2} \quad (2)$$

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 4 shows micrographs of a hybrid bicomponent fiber manufactured by kiss-roll coating with a solution of 5 wt% poly(ester-amide) in trichloromethane at a fiber speed of 14 m s^{-1} . The transverse images a)-d) show rather rough coatings which seem to surround the glass core. The cross-sections e), f) reveal that the coating tends to form a surrounding sheath but can also result in the polymer being

deposited only on one side, as shown in Fig. 4g). All cross-sections e)-g) exhibit fiber volume fractions above the intended range from 50% to 70%, indicating that an even higher fiber speed would be suitable in combination with the chosen process parameters.

Figure 4: Scanning electron micrographs of a glass fiber kiss-roll coated with a solution of 5 wt% poly(ester-amide) in trichloromethane at a fiber speed of 14 m s^{-1} , a peripheral roll speed of 1.88 m s^{-1} and a roll radius of 0.1 m.

This shows that kiss-roll coating with a dilute polymer solution is a suitable method for the fabrication of hybrid bicomponent fibers in-line with glass melt spinning, which can be conducted in a range of drawing speeds v from 8 m s^{-1} to 83 m s^{-1} [4, 7].

Fig. 5 shows micrographs of fibers produced within the parameter study. All fibers shown were drawn over a kiss-roll with a radius of 0.05 m and a peripheral roll speed of 1 m s^{-1} which was immersed in a solution of 8 wt% poly(ester-amide) in trichloromethane, with fiber speeds ranging from 0.8 m s^{-1} to 1.5 m s^{-1} . All fibers a)-c) exhibit rather smooth coatings, with variations in the surface morphology independent of the coating speed. Similar to the high-speed trials, a variation in sheath thickness can be observed within the cross-sectional images of the fibers. Mostly concentric coatings were observed d), while some sections f), g) reveal an asymmetric configuration like the ones observed in Fig. 4e)-g). Note that the same qualities of the coating were observed for all other parameter settings as well.

The observed variations are not considered problematic for further processing of bicomponent fibers, as the coating will always be re-melted for consolidation and forming into a composite part. It is however important that the mean coating thickness stays constant at the mesoscale to obtain preforms which result in laminates of a constant and homogeneous fiber volume fraction. Still, the presence of excessive variations increases the risk that the coating is sheared off due to frictional loads and interlocking during textile processing of bundles of bicomponent fibers. This is expected to be additionally influenced by the mechanical properties of the thermoplastic polymer itself as well as by its adhesion to the reinforcing fiber core.

Figure 5: Scanning electron micrographs of glass fibers kiss-roll coated with a solution of 8 wt% poly(ester-amide) in trichloromethane at a peripheral roll speed of 1 m s^{-1} , a roll radius of 0.05 m and a fiber speed of a)-c) 0.8 m s^{-1} ; f) 1.7 m s^{-1} ; and d), e), g) 1.5 m s^{-1} .

The mean fiber volume fractions obtained from the complete sets of micrographs are plotted against their corresponding fiber speeds in Fig. 6. Even in these mean values, there is quite a significant scatter, which is attributed to the fact that per parameter combination and fiber speed, only a single fiber was coated and analyzed. However, linear regression of the data still reveals trends with respect to the processing parameters.

Comparing the data in the top row for $w_p = 8 \text{ wt}\%$ (+, dotted) to the one for $w_p = 10 \text{ wt}\%$ (x, dashed) reveals that a lower polymer concentration results in a shift of the curves towards higher fiber speeds. This is explained by a change in the coating fluid's properties: a lower polymer concentration leads to a lower viscosity, which in turn leads to lower capillary numbers Ca (Eq. 3).

$$Ca_f = \frac{\eta v}{\gamma} \text{ at the fiber, } Ca_r = \frac{\eta U}{\gamma} \text{ at the roll} \quad (3)$$

Figure 6: Mean fiber volume fraction versus fiber speed and corresponding linear trendlines of all experimental sets within the two-level full factorial parameter study.

Assuming that the transfer of the fluid from the kiss-roll to the fiber behaves like dip-coating (Eq. 4) [3], reducing the polymer concentration reduces η and a higher fiber speed v would be needed to achieve the same capillary number and thus the same coating thickness h and fiber volume fraction. Note that density ρ and surface tension γ of the coating solution are not significantly affected by changes in polymer concentration in the range studied [2].

$$\frac{h}{r} \propto Ca^n, \quad n \sim \frac{2}{3} \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the transfer of the fluid from the reservoir bath to the roll can be modeled as dip-coating of a curved plate, which is withdrawn from the bath at an angle of contact θ [8, 9]. The expectation is that an increase in the peripheral roll speed U leads to an increase in the capillary number at the roll, yielding a thicker fluid film available for the fiber to pick up and thus resulting in a higher coating thickness at the fiber, which corresponds to a lower fiber volume fraction. The middle row of Fig. 6 indicates that this decrease in fiber volume fraction following an increased roll speed can be observed for a large roll radius R , while the parameter combination of a low polymer concentration and small roll radius seem to lead to an opposing behavior. It is evident though that an increase or decrease in roll speed does have a noticeable influence on the yielded fiber volume fraction, which suggests that this parameter could be actively varied to gain control over the process. In glass spinning fed by a re-melt bushing, variations in melt temperature and hydrostatic pressure call for adjustments in fiber take-up speed to yield filaments of constant thickness, which would however also alter the thickness of the polymer solution coating. On-line measurements of fiber width before and after coating would allow the implementation of a feedback loop for an accurate control of the roll speed to compensate for these variations inherent to the process.

The model derived by Tharmalingam and Wilkinson [8, 9] indicates that a larger roll radius R yields a higher film thickness on the roll, thus suggesting a higher coating thickness on the fiber. A look at the bottom row of results in Fig. 6 confirms this only for the combination of the low polymer concentration with the high peripheral roll speed, while the other combinations either show the opposite influence or no noticeable influence. Keep in mind that the angles of contact between the fiber and the roll, α and β , were kept constant in the experiments, thus scaling the contact length between the fiber and the roll proportionally to the roll radius. These results suggest that the reported variation in polymer concentration and peripheral roll speed have a higher influence on the coating thickness than the roll radius and that coupled effects do occur.

5 CONCLUSION

Glass filaments kiss-roll coated with poly(ester-amide) at a fiber speed of 14 m s^{-1} yielded hybrid bicomponent fibers with a fiber volume fraction close to the range of 50% to 70%, thus proving that this coating method can be integrated in-line with glass melt spinning.

The observed results of a two-level full factorial parameter study indicate that the highest fiber speed v for the fabrication of hybrid bicomponent fibers of a given fiber volume fraction is achieved mainly through a minimization of the polymer concentration w_p . Note though that in the used setup, there is a limitation to the highest achievable fiber speed induced by the available distance between the coating application and the first contact point of the coated fiber with either the take-up bobbin or with other filaments at a gathering shoe earlier on. A higher fiber speed could thus mean that the surface of the coating does not dry before reaching the next contact point.

The obtained results suggest that a maximization of peripheral roll speed U and roll radius R would further benefit a higher material throughput, although further investigation is needed to support this claim. It is still evident though that the peripheral roll speed could be used as a control input for the in-line coating process.

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